

NORDES DOCTORAL CONSORTIUM PROPOSAL

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MOVE FAST, BREAK THINGS –goes the social axiom of the *tech world*. A pervasive logic that demands the ‘rapid development’ of novel products from the *design world*. It describes the requirement to be the ‘first to market’ to gain competitive advantage in the *business world*. The consequences of this mantra have led us into a realm far beyond the promise of the open web in the *everyday world*.

We, the public, have been left to sift through the rubble of these *broken things* –the disruption to our privacy, the commodification of our behavior, the datafication of the human experience, the disenfranchisement of its citizens, the seizing of our autonomy, the expropriation of our inheritance to a fairer and more just future.

The relentless erosion of the public sphere is happening at a quickening pace. Our democratic institutions cannot compete with the breakneck progress of technology monopolizing every aspect of our lives. And increasingly, the field of design is in thrall to this unstoppable force. But does it have to be this way?

If we could design digital technologies that optimized for the public good, what kind of society could we build? Could a new generation of digital tools, fueled by data, aid in decision-making processes for the public interest?

These are some of the inquiries shaping my research topic: *Designing Mechanisms for Public Deliberation on Data Use*. As an Early-Stage Researcher (ESR) I am positioned within the research program *Design Competence for our Digital Future* (DCODE) –a European network and PhD Program under the umbrella of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Networks (H2020-MSCA-ITN- 2020) within the European Horizon 2020 Framework Program.

One of the research areas of the program is on *Systems of Data Governance*, which is concerned with the norms, principles and rules governing the spread of data across decentralized networks. It addresses the question of: *How can designers enable democratic forms and mechanisms of transparency and data governance?*

The idea of data platforms built for the public good inhabit a negative space left vacant by the current technological landscape. Should design claim this empty space? If so, could user-centered approaches provide a basis to understand people’s *needs*?

How to move from the design tools of late-stage capitalism –of predicting and manufacturing *desires* in users– and creat tools that empower publics –in predicting and fulfilling the *needs* of citizens? How to achieve equity with these technological advancements? This is the in-between I wish to explore.